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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date 5-6.02.2025

Unit name	Ca'Foscari University in Venice
Country	Italy
Number of researchers	1480
Number of students	17400
Link to the website	https://www.unive.it/pag/13526
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	<p>Ca' Foscari has a strong commitment to excellence in research, to the development of international partnerships, to the promotion of talent and to the funding of promising researchers.</p> <p>The Ca' Foscari Research Hub for Global Challenges brings six Research Institutes, focused on societal, economic, and environmental challenges under one roof to ensure synergies, resource optimization, and increase research impact.</p> <p>The aim of the Hub is to provide a stimulating, cutting-edge environment for scientific exchange and cross-fertilisation across disciplines and geographical areas. It promotes an interdisciplinary approach to research. It aims to find competitive solutions to the challenges facing our society by taking advantage of international funding opportunities.</p>

Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

Yes

No

If so:

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1.	<p>What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?</p> <p>Scientific research assumes significant importance in Ca' Foscari's overall strategy and is one of the elements with the highest impact on the university performance and quality assessment exercises carried out periodically by ANVUR (Italian National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes).</p> <p>The quality of the research conducted at Ca' Foscari is also the subject of internal evaluation processes, consistent with government standards and related to resources' allocation.</p> <p>There is no specific regulation by the Rector - everything is based on external regulations National agency for evaluation / accreditation process Maximum 4 publications per person/ budget depends on results In the employment contract it is stated that you have to do research and the salary upgrade depends on scientific results</p>
2.	<p>What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?</p> <p>Once a 5 years – evaluation institution Annual assessment of researchers - Self assessment</p>
3.	<p>What are the basic assessment criteria?</p> <p>Quantitative indicators – coherence between objectives of departments, using of resources – not overall evaluation – only focus on department selected by agency (according to teaching programmes) Publication track of last 3 years Maximum 9 the best publication Differ at the department - each department determines for itself how to evaluate with regard to the specifics of the discipline</p> <p>0-100 points – system</p>
4.	<p>Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?</p> <p>Academic achievements are taken into account when hiring, but later in the career Only one publication is sufficient to receive a pass mark - there is no differentiation at this stage</p>
5.	<p>How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?</p> <p>There are appropriate provisions in the employment contract and have advanced onboarding e.g. Ricerca Day, Welcome Day etc.</p>

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6.	Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?
	No – based mainly on national rules
7.	Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?
	No, because there is total freedom in research and they don't want to impose a development direction Working research group - discussions on research plans/strategy in group or as a department Self assessment – evidence as paper published
8.	Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?
	Yes - support of library At national level – electronic platform
9.	Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?
	Partially – library support
10.	Does the assessment of scientific achievements take into account bibliometric indicators??
	Yes, also general classification of journals (a,b,c list),
11.	Do the assessment criteria take into account elements considered as Open Science?
	No directly
12.	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)
	Not often – mainly depends on legislative changes
13.	Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?
	High quality publication are necessary for habilitation – and that is more recognizable as important than individual assessment itself

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	In career important Economic incentives - upgrade salary every year
14.	Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?
	Quality is important – but no directly. It is more or less collectively work for quality, excellence, recognition, visibility
15.	Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?
	No In individual assessment- number of grants is not taken into account